

A Research-based approach in finding the Correlation between Scientific Principles stated by Vedic Period Rishis and Modern Scientists

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ABSTRACT:

In this paper, a discussion has been carried out on some very valuable scientific theory and principles implemented by Indian Ancient Rishis and Munis which was later discovered by scientists. Some of these include atomic theory, principles of motions, battery generation techniques, Ayurveda, plant science, surgery, the theory of gravity, aerospace, the invention of zero, pi, theory of relativity and time, Sphericity of earth, the architectural concept in the Vedas, and motion of the earth, Chemical Engineering, Military based instruments, etc. discussed during Vedic period. Again a strong, short, and pointed correlation has been established between these scientific principles, theories with modern inventions. This paper also states how current modern laws and principles have already been stated and explained during the Indian Vedic period in the form of Sanskrit shloka and Upanishad in well-explained and logical manners that were used and credits given to other country scientists. The objective of this paper is to conveying information on the advanced technology implementation which was existed during the Indian Vedic period before long years ago and which was adopted all over the rest of the world later we accepted. The authors are also trying to convey the information related to the least negative effects of Vedic technology for living beings, earth, and atmosphere. Here, an attempt has been made for dragging out the versatility and uniquely identifiability of Indian Vedic science and technology in front of the world which is the main motto of this paper.

Keywords: Acharya Kanad, Agastya Samhita, Aryabhata, Charak, Vimana, Shakuna Vimana, Bhardwaj, Vastu Sastra, Dragon 1

1. INTRODUCTION

Indians said that the first aircraft was made by Indians but others laughed. Indian Veda said that they discovered the solar system was round while the western scientists were busy claiming that the earth was flat. But now, the people who laughed at Indians are agreeing that India is the hub of knowledge. Western scientists accepted that Veda is full of knowledge. When the Universities of Manchester and Exeter team researched Veda, they found that Veda had passed on their knowledge to Jesuit missionaries during their visit to India in the fifteenth century which is then was passed on to Isaac Newton eventually[1]. Some principles which were claimed/invented by a different scientist, physicist and for which these scientists, physics feeling proud, taking so many credits have already mentioned and explained very elaborately in Veda since long years ago. This is not just a guess or not a flying statement; this is facts that are not easily digesting by many people in the world now. Vedic Science, Some facts, theories, principles, and laws of the modern period and their correlation with Indian Vedic periods have been discussed in the next sections.

2. VEDIC SCIENCE

The name "Vedic Science" thus indicates both the ancient traditional origins of this body of knowledge and the modern commitment to experience, system, testability, and the demand that knowledge is useful in improving the quality of human life.

(a) Scientist/ Researcher (b) Rishi/Muni

Fig.1: Two Eminent persons whose contribution towards science can never be forgettable

It is a combination of science and spirituality.

3. AN INTERRELATION BETWEEN THE LAWS AND PRINCIPLES OF MODERN AND VEDIC PERIODS

In these modern times, so many laws and principles have been stated by many scientists and researchers. But the facts behind these laws and principles are based on their connection with Vedic science. These can be elaborately discussed below.

3.1 Newton Law of Motion

The great and famous scientist, astronomer, physicist Sir Isaac Newton presented three laws of motion in the year 1686. Its interrelations with Vedic time principles and laws have been discussed.

3.1.1 Newton 1st law of motion by (Acharya Kanad)

Before Newton discovered the laws of Motion, Indian scientist and philosopher (Acharya Kanad) had already given this law of motion in Vaisheshika Sutra (in 600 BCE) which describes the relationship between force and motion, etc.

वेगःनिमित्तविशेषातकर्मणोजायते |वेगःनिमित्तविशेषातकर्मणोजायते |[2]

Vegah: nimittavisheshatakarmanojayate |

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Meaning: Change of motion is due to impressed force.

Fig.2: Newton 1st law of motion stated by Acharya Kanad in Vedic Period

The above law stated that an object at rest tends to stay at rest and an object in motion tends to stay in motion with the same speed and in the same direction unless acted upon by an unbalanced force.

3.1.2 Newton 2nd law of motion by (Acharya Kanad)

वेगःनिमित्तापेक्षातकर्मणोजायतेनियतदिकक्रियाप्रबन्धहेतु ||2]

Vegah:nimittapekshatakarmaṇojaayateniyatadikakriyaaprabandhahetu |

Meaning: Change of motion is proportional to the impressed force and is in the direction of the force.

Fig.3: Newton 2ndlaw of motion stated by Acharya Kanad in Vedic Period

3.1.3 Newton's 3rd Law of Motion (By Acharya Kanad)

वेगःसंयोगविशेषविरोधी|[10]

Vegah: sanyogavisheshavirodhee |

Meaning: Action and reaction are equal and opposite.

Fig.4: Newton 3rdlaw of motion stated by Acharya Kanad in Vedic Period

3.2 The Atomic Theory

An English chemist and physicist named John Dalton (1766 – 1844) is the man who is taking credits today of developing atomic theory. But the real fact is that nearly 2,500 years before John Dalton, Acharya Kanad, an ancient Hindu sage, and philosopher also called as Kashyap had already stated that every object in the creation is made up of atoms which in turn connected to form molecules and this statement later used by John Dalton in his atomic theory. The interesting story behind Acharya Kanad's name was he passed his knowledge onto others, and so people then started referring him as 'Acharya'; the teacher and the meaning of 'Kan' in Sanskrit is 'the smallest particle'. Hence he became famous by the name of (Acharya Kanad) or 'the teacher of small particles' eventually.

Fig.5: Acharya Kanad- The Teacher of Small Particles [google]

When Kashyap(Acharya Kanad) was on a pilgrimage to Prayag, he saw thousands of pilgrims litter the streets with flowers and rice grains, which they offered at the temple. Kashyap, engrossed by small particles, started collecting the grains of rice. A crowd gathered around him to see the strange man collecting grains from the street. The crowd then asked the question to Kashyap, why he was collecting the grains that even a beggar wouldn't touch. He said those crowds that individual grains in themselves may seem worthless, but if some hundreds of grains will be collected then it can make up a person's meal and these collections of many meals can feed an entire family and eventually, the whole mankind was made of many families. This logical analysis concluded that even a single grain of rice has the same value and the same importance as like as all the valuable riches in this world. Acharya Kanad described the "invisible matter" as "Paramanu" or "Anu" which translated meaning is "atom" in this modern science. Again Acharya Kanad explained one deepest and very important concept that neither these invisible matters could be sensed through any human organ, nor could be it be seen or observed by the human naked eyes. Further, Acharya Kanad speculated the existence of Anu or a small indestructible particle, similar to an atom. He also explained that Anu can have two states – absolute peace and a state of movement. He continues to hold the atoms of the same substance combined and in a specific manner synchronized dvyanuka (diatomic molecule) to generate and tryanuka (triatomic molecules). He again theorized that different mixtures of "anu" will produce very different types of substances and he presented all the objects of creation into nine elements such as 1.Earth, 2.Water, 3.Light, or Fire, 4.Wind, 5.Ether, 6.Time, 7.Space, 8.Mind, and 9.Soul. "Every object of creation is made of atoms which in turn connect with each other to form molecules," – (Acharya Kanad) [3].

3.3 Invention of DC Battery

Rishi Agastya wrote a book named Agastya Samhita that describes the strategy of creating an electrical battery. He explained that water is split into oxygen and hydrogen. The battery cell resembles Agastya's methodology of generating electricity. He was the primary Dry cell inventor which generates D.C current, hence he was also creditable for electricity generation. [4]

Fig.6: DC Battery Cell in the Vedic Period

3.4 Discovery of Number System (zero, pi)

Fig.7: The great Indian Mathematician Aryabhata

It is wide well-known that the great Indian mathematician Aryabhata was invented this golden value called “zero (0)”one (1). Mathematician Aryabhata was the first person, which is a symbol for zero, and it was through his efforts, the mathematical operations such as addition and subtraction create the figure starts with zero [5]. The concept of zero and the integration into the value system activated and writing a number, no matter how large, only ten symbols. These two digits one (1) and zero (0) discovered by Aryabhata is now become the backbone of electronics science and play an enormous role in mathematical science. The first time he had calculated the value of π at 3.1416.

3.5 Sign Convention

Symbol, signs Associate in Nursing notation were used in an early kind in India by the sixth century once the mathematician-astronomer Aryabhata suggested the employment of letters to represent unknown quantities [6].

3.6 Atomism and Quantum Physics

India proposed and developed very early about the atomic theories of matter. Greek atomistic thought influenced by India via the Persian civilization can be a possibility. The Vedic Aryans gave the world some of the earliest philosophical concepts on the structure of matter and a theoretically strong foundation for the chemical structure of minerals. Thousands of years before Christ, those Sanskrit Vedas gave conclusions that matter could not be created, and also that the universe had created itself. Using this philosophical reflection, Kanada (600 B.C) in his Vaisheshika philosophy revealed that elements could not be destroyed. Somewhat at Kanada's life is mysterious, but his name is said to mean “one who eats particle or grain” likely referring to his concept that basic particles mix collectively as the building blocks for all matter. Two, three, four, or additional of these elements would mix, even as we tend to imagine atoms doing. The Greeks wouldn't come across this idea for another century [7].

4. VEDIC SCIENCE CONTRIBUTION TO THE WORLD OF MEDICINE AND VETERINARY

The contribution of Veda in medicine and veterinary can't possible to count. Some of the outstanding works can be discussed below.

4.1 Cataract Surgery

Fig.8: Sushruta- Father of Indian Medicine and Father of Plastic Surgery [8]

The first cataract surgery is said to have been carried out by the ancient Indian physician Sushruta, way back in the 6th century BCE. To remove the cataract from the eye, he used a curved needle, Jabamukhi Salaka to release the lens and pushed the cataract out of sight. The eye would then be bandaged for a few days until it is fully healed. Sushruta the surgical work was later translated into Arabic and the Arabs, his works were introduced to the West [9].

4.2 Plant Science:

Varahamihira's book PanchSiddhanta noted that the moon and the planets are lustrous not because of their own light but due to sunlight. He had great contributions in the fields of Hydrology, geology, maths, and ecology [10]. He had given important information about termites (insects that destroy woods or dimak) is that they go very deep to the surface of water level to bring water to keep their houses wet. Moreover, he was the first mathematician to discover a version of what is now known as Pascal's triangle. He used it to calculate binomial coefficients [11].

4.3 Ayurveda

Long before the birth of Hippocrates, Charaka authored a seminal text, Charaka Samhita, on the ancient science of Ayurveda. Referred to as the father of Indian medicine, Charakawas the first physician to present the concept of digestion metabolism and immunity in his book. Charaka the old manual on preventive medicine remained a standard work on the subject for two thousand years and has been translated into many languages, including Arabic and Latin.

4.4 Astronomy

Indian Veda also has a large contribution to the field of astronomy. Some of these are given below.

4.4.1 Theory of Gravity

It is well-known to the world that "The Universal Law of Gravitation" was discovered by Sir Isaac Newton when he saw an apple fell from a tree. The world believes that Newton was the first person to discover the earth's gravitational concept. Now if someone wants to reveal the actual truth, then he or she can find that during 400-500 AD, an Indian treatise named 'Surya Siddhanta' written in the ancient Sanskrit script has already explained about the concept of gravity [12]. This treatise is a formal and systematic written discourse on the deep concept of astronomy. In this Surya Siddhant treatise, Bhaskaracharya explained that earth has a gravitational force (in Sanskrit it is called gurutvaakarshanshakti) and there does a mutual attraction exists between the planets and this allows them to hold themselves finally in space [13]. The statement is "Objects fall on the earth due to a force of attraction by the earth". Therefore, the earth, planets, constellations, moon, and sun are held in orbit due to this force. Approximately after 1200 years (1687 AD), Sir Isaac Newton rediscovered this phenomenon and named it as "The Law of Gravity". This law of Gravity was mentioned in Veda written in the form of shloka which is given below.

I. Rig Veda 8.12.28

"O Indra! By putting forth your mighty rays, which possess the qualities of gravitation and attraction-illumination and motion – keep up the entire universe in order through the Power of your attraction." [14]

II. Rig Veda 1.6.5, Rig Veda 8.12.30

"O God, you have created this Sun. You possess infinite power. You are upholding the sun and other spheres and render them steadfast by your power of attraction [15]

III. Yajur Veda 33.43

"The sun moves in its own orbit in space taking along with itself the mortal bodies like earth through force of attraction." [14]

IV. Rig Veda 1.35.9

"The sun moves in its own orbit but holding earth and other heavenly bodies in a manner that they do not collide with each other through force of attraction." [14]

V. Rig Veda 1.164.13

"Sun moves in its orbit which itself is moving. Earth and other bodies move around sun due to force of attraction, because sun is heavier than them." [15]

VI. Atharva Veda 4.11.1

"The sun has held the earth and other planets" [16]

4.4.2 Eclipse

“O Sun! When you are blocked by the one whom you gifted your own light (moon), and then the earth gets scared by sudden darkness.”
-Rig Veda 5.40.5 [17]

4.4.3 Light of Moon

“The moving moon always receives a ray of light from the sun”- Rig Veda 1.84.15

4.4.4 Motion of Earth

“This earth is devoid of hands and legs, yet it moves ahead. All the objects over the earth also move with it. It moves around the Sun. - Rig Veda 10.22.14”.

“The sun has tied Earth and other planets through attraction and moves them around itself as if a trainer moves newly trained horses around itself holding their reins.”-Rig Veda 10.149.1

4.4.5 Sphericity of Earth

“O God, You have created this Sun. You possess infinite power. You are upholding the sun and other spheres and render them steady by your power of attraction.”-Rig Veda 1.6.5, Rig Veda 8.12.30

Aitareya Brahmana (3.44) declares: The Sun does never set nor rise. When people think the Sun is setting, it is not so. For after having arrived at the end of the day it makes itself produce two opposite effects, making night to what is below and day to what is on the other side.

Fig.9: Origin of Planets as described in Vishnu Puran [16]

Having reached the end of the night, it makes itself produce two opposite effects, making day to what is below and night to what is on the other side. In fact, the Sun never sets [18].

‘Shape of Earth is like an Oblate Spheroid. (Rig Veda 30.4.5)
‘Earth is flattened at the poles’ (Markandeya Purana 54.12)

4.5 Speed of Sunlight through Yajurveda

Velocity of Light was calculated by Maxwell in the 19th century but Speed of Light was determined accurately in Rig Veda thousands of years ago. It was further elaborated by Sayana in 14th century AD. The fourth verse of the Rig-Vedic hymn 1:50 (50th hymn in the book of Rig-Veda) is as follows:

तरणिविश्वदर्शतो जयोतिष्कृदसिसूर्य | विश्वमाभासिरोचनम | taraNirvishvadarshato jyotishkrdasisurya |
vishvamaabhaasirochanam ||

It means “Swift and all beautiful art thou, O Surya (Surya=Sun), maker of the light, Illuming the entire radiant realm”. Sayana who was a minister in the court of Bukka of the great Vijayanagar Empire of Karnataka in South India (in early 14th century) in his Rigvedic interpretation; commenting on this verse that:

“tatha ca smaryateyojananam. sahasredvedve sate dve ca yojaneekenanimishardhenakramaman” .

It means “It is remembered here that Sun (light) traverses 2,202 yojanas in half a nimisha”

In the Vedas Yojana is a unit of distance and Nimisha is a unit of time. So now, the value of the speed of light in modern units can be calculated as follows: 2202 yojanas in 1/2 nimesa = 2202 x 9.09 miles per 0.1056 seconds = 20016.18 miles per 0.1056 seconds = **189547 miles per second!! That is as per the Rig Veda.**

As per the modern science **speed of light given by Maxwell is 186000 miles per second!** Hence, there is the slightest difference between the two values to our error in accurately translating from Vedic units to SI/CGS units.

4.6 Distance between Earth and Sun (Mention in Hanuman Chalisa)

There is a shloka written in Hanuman Chalisa as:

“Yugsahasrayojana par bhanu,

leelyotaahimadhura phal jaanu

The above shloka means to: When Hanuman travelled thousands of kilometers to swallow Sun thinking of it as a fruit (Fig. 5)

The word-to-word translation of the same shloka reveals the distance that Hanuman travelled.
1 Yuga = 12000 years. 1 Sahsa Yuga = 12000000 years. Also, 1 Yojan = 8 miles.

Hence in “YugSahasraYojana”, the first 3 words mean 12000000*8 = 96000000 miles (1miles=1.6 km) or 153,600,000 kilometers. Interestingly, the actual distance from the earth to the sun is 152,000,000 km, bafflingly, there's an error of just around 1%.

4.7 Blue Colour of Sky

“BlueSkyisnothingbutscattered sunlight”(MarkandeyaPurana78.8)

ModernsciencesaysaboutitthatthebluecoloroftheskyisduetoRayleighscattering. Aslightmovesthroughtheatmosphere,mostofthelongerwavelengthspassstraightthrough. Littleofthered, orange, andyellowlightisaffectedbytheair. [7]

4.8 Theory of Relativity and Time

TothephilosophersofIndia,Relativityisnonewdiscovery,justastheconceptofflightyears isnomatterforastonishment topeopleusedto thinkingoftimeinmillions of Kalpas,(AKalpaisabout4,320,000years). ThefactthatthewisemenofIndiahavenotbeenconcernedwithtechnological applicationsofthisknowledgearisesfromthecircumstancethattechnologyisbutoneofinnumerablewaysofapplyingit. Itis,indeed,a stimulatingcircumstancethatoncewesterncivilizationdiscoversrelativity,itappliesittothemanufactureofatom-bombs,whereasOrientalcivilizationappliesittothedevelopmentofnewstatesofconsciousness [7].

5. DEVELOPMENT OF AEROPLANE

Maharishi Bhardwaj in the Vedic Age spoke of the existence of aeroplanes around 7,000 years ago. Then after Wright brothers invented the aeroplanes. Vaimanika Shastra written by Maharishi Bhardwaj had become a part of the Rig Veda worked on the science of aircraft technology. He discussed about the modelling of Vimana named Tripura Vimana, Rukma Vimana, Sundara Viman, and Shakuna Vimana [19, 20]

(a) Top View of Shakuna Vimana &Space X Dragon

(b) Side View of Shakuna Vimana &Space X Dragon

Fig.11: Shakuna Vimana Vs.Space X Dragon (Top and side view)

Modern Scientists copied those models in many ways. For example, the Space X Dragon, also known as Dragon 1 or Cargo Dragon is a reusable cargo spacecraft developed by Space X, launched in 2020 by an American private space Transportation Company having modelled the same as Shakuna Vimana.

6. ARCHITECTURAL CONCEPT IN THE VEDAS

The science of VasthuSatra, which concerns with the layouts and the direction of building architecture and is hot a current topic the world over, is traceable to at least the year 3000BC in the Vedas. The Gumbaz found on the mosques all over the world actually originated as the interlocking dome in the Stupa of the Buddhist architectural tradition in India. The temple architecture found all over India speaks volumes for the design concept related to engineering. The buildings of huge structures without the use of any modern equipment actually tell the story of advanced feat in construction practices.

7. STUDY OF SPACE AND MILITARY RELATED CONCEPTS IN THE VEDAS

Dhanur Veda explains in great detail the organization of armed forces i.e. the military of the times. Well-defined rules have been laid out regarding armaments and warfare. There was also mention of missiles and other weapons in the literature. It is really amazing that conceptually the rules and arts are comparable to modern times. There were also well-planned traps known as Viyuhas to capture the enemy. These well-defined strategies are given names based on their shapes like Padma (lotus), chakra (circle), virichika (scorpion), etc; Spacecrafts are referred to as *pustpakvimanas* in the literature and surprisingly their mode of take off exactly resembles that of modern aircraft. Eclipses are predicted well in advance of their occurrence and this clearly proves that astronomy and space science were prevailing at great heights [21].

8. CONCLUSION

The principles, theories related to science, and technologies written in Veda were highly advanced at that time which was accepted by the maximum scientists of India and mainly outside of India. Also, they worked, and

later they proved those principles and theories. We Indians and the rest of the world accepted their inventions after the justifications. Some of the scientists told their opinion about Veda and Upanishad such as:

Albert Einstein "When I read the Bhagavad- Gita and reflect about how God created this universe everything else seems so superfluous"

Erwin Schrodinger "The unity and continuity of Vedanta are reflected in the unity and continuity of wave mechanics"

Nicola Tesla "The gift of mental power comes from God, divine being, and if we concentrate our mind on truth, we become in tune with this great power. Our senses enable us to perceive only a minute portion of the outside world"

Niels Bohr "I go into Upanishads to ask questions"

SrinivasaRamanujan "An Equation has no meaning unless it expresses a thought of GOD"

Werner Heisenberg "After the conversation about Indian philosophy, some of these ideas of quantum physics that had seemed so crazy suddenly made much more sense. Quantum theory will not look ridiculous to people who have read Vedanta"

Dr. SubhashKak "The Vedic approach might be useful in obtaining further advancing in the field of science and technologies"

By the statement of those above great scientists and researchers, it can be easily concluded that Indian Veda is highly demanded, appreciated, and accepted globally. But we Indians understood when scientists accepted that Veda played an important role in their inventions. In the Vedic period, inventions are environmentally friendly and are having the least side effects on living beings. In ancient times, Rishis warned the kings of every Yug (all four) not to make mahayantras (Advanced Machines). Otherwise, it will destroy the resources of mother earth or the future human generations would face wrath in the form of shrinking of land, changes weather, floods, earthquakes, and loss of species. The present era demands a dialogue between Vedic and Modern science so that the right place and value may be given to both the sciences. So now, the Indian government is focusing on the research for the advancement of technologies through Veda.

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